

Magnetic domain observation on (110)[001] Fe-Si steel at elevated temperature

Shayan Deldar ^{1*} and Rudolf Schäfer ^{1,2}

¹ Leibniz Institute for Solid State and Materials Research (IFW) Dresden

² Institute for Materials Science, TU Dresden

* Correspondence: s.deldar@ifw-dresden.de

Abstract: Magnetic domains of a (110)[001] grain-oriented electrical steel (GOES) were investigated at temperatures up to 550 °C utilizing magneto-optical Kerr effect (MOKE) microscopy. Elevation of temperature resulted in the disappearance of lancet domains and reduction of the slap domain width. The domain width also showed an inverse relationship with the demagnetization frequency. Finally, this work presents a detailed characterization of the magnetization process of GOES at high temperatures taking into account the external magnetic field direction. The magnetic domain patterns observed at high temperature in transverse field are known from room temperature observations, but they only appear on a much thicker GOES sheet. We conclude that at elevated temperatures the contribution of magnetostrictive energy to the total energy increases and dictates the domain character.

Keywords: grain-oriented electrical steel; magnetic domains; Kerr microscopy; magnetization; misorientation; transverse magnetic field, EMPIR 19ENG06 HEFMAG

1. Introduction

With the ascending interest in electrically powered transportation and renewable energy, the production of more efficient transformers and electric motors/generators is gaining increasing attention. A low-loss silicon steel core with high permeability is essential to any efficient electrical machinery. As the application of these machines becomes more and more common, longer uninterrupted working hours at harsher environmental conditions may lead to higher working temperatures. Therefore, studying the magnetic properties of the core material at elevated temperatures is crucial for the understanding and improvement of electrical steel material. The operating temperature of the core material in a traction motor in an electric vehicle or a power transformer can reach up to 400 °C [1,2]. For curiosity, we even go to higher temperatures in this work. Furthermore, research on silicon steels at elevated temperatures primarily focused on integral magnetic properties in the past, such as saturation magnetization, coercivity, and loss [3–8]. Very few studies aimed at the investigation of magnetic domain structures with respect to temperature (T). A work by Kranz and Brunner [9] is a rare example.

Understanding the change of magnetic domains with increasing temperature requires knowledge about the temperature dependence of the energy terms that determine the domain character [10]: domain wall energy (E_w), stray field energy (E_d), and magnetostrictive self energy (E_{el}). The domain wall energy density (γ_w), which is defined as the value of the domain wall energy per unit wall area (F), is proportional to $\sqrt{A \cdot K}$ (A : exchange energy density, K : magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant). In a ferromagnet, a coarser domain structure with fewer domain walls leads to a reduction of the wall energy. The stray field energy is related to the presence of magnetic poles in the magnetic medium. In the case of basic slap domain pattern in an iron-silicon crystal with (110)-surface, E_d is proportional to $W \cdot J_s^2 \cdot \sin^2 \theta$ (W : slap domain width, J_s : saturation polarization, θ : out-of-plane misorientation angle of the surface-parallel [001] axis). Generally, a smaller misorientation or narrower basic domain width at a given misorientation reduces the stray field energy. A further reduction can be achieved by supplementary domain patterns that are superimposed to the basic domains. In Goss-textured transformer steel material, the interplay of the mentioned energy terms leads to the formation of the well-known lancet domains. The detailed domain wall orientation is finally determined by the magnetostrictive self energy density (γ_{el}), which is defined as the value of magnetostrictive self energy per unit volume and which is proportional to $G \cdot \lambda^2$ (G : shear modulus of the material, λ : magnetostriction constant). For a review on the interplay of energies in the Goss-textured materials, we refer to [11]

The domain wall energy density, similar to stray field energy, steadily declines as temperature climbs [9]. On the contrary, the magnetostrictive self energy density increases within the temperature range of interest [12]. The temperature influences these energy terms through the parameters such as the exchange energy, saturation

magnetization, shear modulus, and magnetostriction coefficient [4,13]. The domain structure of a ferromagnet at any arbitrary temperature is determined by the minimalization of the collective values of E_w , E_d , and E_{el} .

Kranz [9] suggested that in a perfectly oriented (110) surface, the slap domain width is determined solely by the magnetostrictive energy of the domain structure and the domain wall energy. The stray field is eliminated by closure domain formation. Their employed specimens were demagnetized at defined temperatures by a 50 Hz decaying AC magnetic field. The decay time and amplitude of the AC field were not specified. They reported that the width of the (110) slap domains was reduced by 75 % of its room temperature value at 400 °C, plateaus until 600 °C, and increased afterward.

The demagnetization frequency (f_d) was also reported to affect the slap domain width of the (110) surface [14,15]. Higher demagnetization frequency generally results in a smaller average slap domain width because the opposing local magnetic field created by the eddy currents around moving domain walls prevents the domain wall motion from exceeding a larger distance thus leading to a multiplication of the active domain walls [14]. Nevertheless, the amount of the f_d effect on the domain width was reported inconsistently in the literature. Yamamoto et al. [15] illustrated that the slap domain width of the grain-oriented steel was reduced by around 20 % with the increase of demagnetization frequency from 5 to 500 Hz. In comparison, Passon [14] showed a much more substantial reduction in domain width after increasing the demagnetization frequency from 5 to 50 Hz. This matter was examined in this work independently.

A small degree of out-of-plane misorientation of the [001] easy axis results in the formation of the mentioned lancet domains. This effect has been quantitatively studied in the literature via experiments [16] as well as calculations [13,17,18]. The formation of lancets puts the system at higher magnetostrictive and domain wall energy levels. Nevertheless, lancets and their internal transverse domain structure provide a more energy-efficient path to close the magnetic flux, significantly reducing the stray field energy of the system. At higher temperatures, however, the existence of lancet domains becomes less essential since the induced thermal energy already diminishes the stray field energy [13]. Kranz [9] showed that the lancet domains almost completely disappeared by 550 °C.

At a certain in-plane external magnetic field (H) applied at a moderate angle respective to the [001] direction, Lancet domains arrange in a way to share one internal transverse domain. This arrangement of the lancet domains is referred to as the lancet comb structure. This structure was used by Bär et al. [16] to estimate the out-of-plane misorientation angle of GOES.

The thickness of the Fe-Si sheet plays a role for the domain patterns on sheets with (110)-related surface [19]. It is reported that the importance of magnetostrictive energy becomes more pronounced compared to domain wall energy for the thicker sheets and vice versa for thinner ones [10,19]. When subjected to a small external field transverse to the [001] direction, The so-called column pattern is observed on the sheet with 0.3 mm standard thickness. The so-called checkerboard pattern is found for specimens thicker than 0.8 mm and an irregular column pattern on the thinner ones [19]. The checkerboard pattern is magnetostrictively favored compared to the column pattern and is therefore energetically more favorable for thick sheets, whereas the higher magnetostrictive energy of the column patterns is less important for thin sheets as it has a lower domain wall energy [10,19].

2. Materials and Methods

The investigated material was a commercially produced 0.27 mm thick GOES sheet, from which two disk-shaped samples with a diameter of 10 mm were cut out. Both samples were then undergone a standardized metallographic grinding and polishing process to obtain a stress-free flat surface for magnetic domain observation.

Sample 1 was demagnetized with sufficient starting AC field amplitude and different demagnetization frequencies ranging from 1 to 50 Hz. Thus, the domain width dependency on the demagnetization frequency can be compared with [14]. The AC field decaying time was set to 30 seconds and the field amplitude was decreased linearly. The demagnetization process was carried out parallel to the easy direction. The visual domain width measurements were performed at room temperature and up to 550 °C. For this sample, particular attention was paid to the lancet domains to study their annihilation with increasing temperature. Finally, the misorientation angle estimation method (illustrated by Bär et al. [16]) was validated at room temperature and examined at elevated temperatures.

Sample 2 contained multiple grains with a slight variation in the crystallographic orientation, leading to diversification of the domain structure. This sample was used to investigate the magnetic domain behavior throughout the magnetic hysteresis at temperatures up to 550 °C. To achieve that, static domain images were acquired at an incrementally progressing external magnetic field covering the entirety of the magnetic hysteresis loop. This process was carried out in parallel and transverse directions relative to the easy [001] axis.

Magneto-optical Kerr effect (MOKE) microscopy was employed for domain visualization of the samples [20,21]. Difference imaging with background subtraction [22] was used to enhance contrast of the MOKE images. The high-

temperature measurements were carried out in a heating stage setup particularly designed to be incorporated into the Kerr microscope. The sample was heated using a heated copper finger under a vacuum ($\approx 10^{-6}$ mbar). The temperature was monitored by a thermocouple placed underneath the specimen and controlled by a PID regulator. The sample surface was visually accessed through a glass window on top of the vacuum chamber. An electromagnet connected to a power supply applied the external magnetic field. The electromagnet can be rotated by 360° , allowing the application of the field in different directions. Figure 1 shows the schematic illustration and an actual photo of the heating stage setup.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration and photograph of the heating stage adapted to the Kerr microscope.

3. Results and discussion

The effect of temperature and demagnetization frequency on the slap domain width of the (110) surface is presented in Figure 2. The data points were acquired by demagnetizing sample 1 at different frequencies and repeating the process at various temperature levels. An area was selected with close to zero misorientation to obtain an almost perfect slap domain structure. After taking several images for each temperature/frequency level, the average values of the visually measured slap domain width were plotted against temperature (Figure 2a) and demagnetization frequency (Figure 2b). The findings indicate that the domain width decreases at a higher rate below 400°C and starts to plateau afterward. Moreover, the increasing demagnetization frequency had a steadily reducing effect on the average domain width, which was expected [9,14]. The data also show that the temperature effect on the domain width is weaker when demagnetized with a higher f_d . The demagnetizing frequency is obviously less effective for domain width reduction at elevated temperatures.

Figure 2. Average slap domain width of the investigated GOES respective to measurement temperature (a) and demagnetization frequency (b).

The annihilation of the lancet domains at high temperatures was observed on sample 1 at three different locations. Figure 3 represents these locations after demagnetization with $f_d = 10$ Hz at room temperature and up to 500 °C. The AC demagnetization field (H_d) was applied parallel to the easy [001] direction. Out of these three locations, location 1 has the smallest crystallographic misorientation and lancet domains occupy only around 2.5 % of the observed surface at RT. Locations 2 and 3 are more misoriented and consist of roughly 12 and 18 % lancet fractional area at RT. Demagnetization of the specimen at elevated temperature results in an increasing lowering of the lancet population with temperature. The total annihilation of the lancet domains at location 1 occurs at around 200 °C. Lancet domains at locations 2 and 3, despite the decrease in quantity, last up to around 500 °C. For each location, in Figure 4a the mean fractional area of the lancet domains is plotted with respect to temperature. Figure 4b represents a schematic 3D sketch of the slap domain structure at a perfectly oriented (110)[001] grain, and Figure 4c showcases the 3D lancet domain structure in a slightly misoriented grain. The lancet domains on the surface and the transverse domains in the bulk provide a closed path for the magnetic flux with lower energy and hence reduce the stray field energy of the system.

Figure 3. Slap domain structure of the GOES at different temperatures at 3 locations with various misorientation angles. The sample was demagnetized at 10 Hz along [001] axis.

Figure 4. (a) Lancet domain fraction of the imaging surface with respect to the measurement temperature at the 3 locations, as in figure 3. Schematic sketches of slap domains (b) and lancet domains (c) (b) and (c) are adapted from [23].

The noticeable point is that the lancet annihilation temperature (T_a) at locations 2 and 3 is similar despite different initial lancet contents. Iwata et al. [13] presented a diagram in which the *calculated* annihilation temperature was plotted against the out-of-plane misorientation. Their chart indicates that the T_a exhibits a nonlinear dependency on the misorientation angle. A misorientation of 1° compared to 1.5° showed $\Delta T_a \sim 400^\circ\text{C}$, whereas this value for misorientation of 2 to 4° was calculated to be around 60°C . Therefore, determining the out-of-plane misorientation angles of the three locations is necessary to offer an argument concerning the annihilation temperature. Generally, the crystallographic orientation of the grains can be measured via XRD or EBSD [24]. Nevertheless, the method employed in [16] using the linear density of the lancet comb structure was proven reliable within 1 to 10° of out-of-plane misorientation.

To obtain the lancet comb structure (Figure 6b), an in-plane magnetic field of a moderate magnitude was applied to the GOES at some small angle relative to [001] direction. Figure 5 shows the formation of the lancet comb patterns for the same three locations as in Figure 3. After the appearance of the lancet comb domains, the linear density (n) of the lancet combs was measured. The term “linear density” refers to the number of lancets crossed by a one-millimeter-long line parallel to the comb baseline. An example for $n = 4$ is illustrated in Figure 6a. Bär et al. [16] reported that the density of lancets linearly depends on the out-of-plane misorientation. The data points for Bär’s contribution were imported to Figure 6a for comparison purposes (solid triangles). Based on this method, the misorientation angles of the measurement locations were estimated using their linear lancet density at 21°C (hollow squares). After evaluating several images at 21°C with this method, the average misorientation angles for locations 1, 2, and 3 were determined to be 1.06 , 1.65 , and 3.89 degrees, respectively.

After estimating the misorientation angle of the locations based on the lancet comb patterns at RT, the validation of the method at elevated temperatures was examined. Exemplary domain images of locations 1 to 3 at 300 and 500°C are also presented in Figure 5. Hollow circles and star data points in Figure 6a represent the mean value of the linear density of lancets at 300 and 500°C . The data points indicate a steady reduction of the n value at location 3. However, the same rise in temperatures results in a much stronger drop in the n value at locations 1 and 2. Bär [16] stated that below a critical misorientation angle ($\theta_c \sim 1^\circ$) the method was not accurate at room temperature. The presented data suggested that the *effective* θ_c value at 500°C increases to around 2° . Interestingly, the lancets at location 3 do not disappear even up to 500°C , opposite to the observation in Fig.4. The reason is that in case of the lancet *comb* pattern, the common internal plate domains carry some transverse flux as required by the obliquely applied field. The comb pattern therefore needs to be maintained at any temperature for flux reasons, even though the supplementary pattern would not be required anymore for stray field reasons. Interestingly, for locations 1 and 2 there are still small, obliquely running domains left even when lancets have completely disappeared at 500° . As there are no lancets, there cannot be any internal plate domains. It may be that this pattern is related to the so-called saw-ooth pattern [10] that normally develops in fields almost transverse to the [001] axes and that also allows for transverse flux propagation.

Figure 5. Lancet comb domain structure of the GOES at different temperatures at 3 locations. The magnetic field direction relative to [001] axis is shown with the white arrow.

Figure 6. (a) Linear lancet density plotted against the misorientation angle measured at RT (in comparison with [16]), 300 and 500 °C at 3 locations, as in figure 3. (b) Schematic sketch of lancet comb domain structure ((b) is adapted with permission from [25]).

The measurements on sample 2 focused on the magnetization processes at elevated temperatures. In this respect, two grains on sample 2 were selected, G1 with an almost perfect (110)[001] orientation and G2 with a moderate misorientation angle. Figure 7 illustrates the magnetic domains of the two grains in a field sweep from -150 to 150 mT. The magnetic field direction was parallel to the easy direction [001]. As observed in rows a and b of Figure 7, the elevation of T has very little influence on the magnetization process. For grain G2 (rows c and d), the temperature leads

to the mentioned reduction of the lancet density, which is expected according to the prior findings; however, the nature of the magnetic reversal process does not change with temperature.

Figure 7. Magnetization process of the grain-oriented material in a magnetic field along the [001] axis, starting and ending in oppositely saturated states. Rows (a) and (b) represent a close-to-perfect Goss texture at room temperature and 400 °C. Rows (c) and (d) represent a moderate crystallographic misorientation at room temperature and 400 °C. The images illustrate the magnetization process from -150 to +150 mT.

The application of H in the direction transverse to the [001] axis resulted in an interesting phenomenon. Figure 8 shows the domain patterns of GOES observed in an increasing transverse magnetic field from the remanent state ($H = 0$) up to 150 mT. At RT, the domain pattern at the remanent state (slap domain pattern in a_1 or lancet-dense pattern in c_1) is replaced by the column pattern that gets increasingly branched with increasing field finally reaching saturation. This transformation of domains is characteristic for the transverse magnetization process in sheets with *standard* thickness around 0.3 mm [26].

In contrast, at elevated temperature the nature of the magnetization process changes and an unexpected pattern shows up. At the remanent state, G1 shows a slap domain structure (Figure 8b₁) like at room temperature. At G2, the remanent domain structure contains a significantly lower lancet density as expected (d₁). The magnetization process of both grains then follow a similar behavior. At both locations, a checkerboard pattern is formed at small magnetic fields (b₂ and d₂). The process continues by shrinking the unfavorable checkerboard cells as well as folding and branching of

the separating walls forming the so-called cord pattern (b_3 and d_3). These cord domains then broaden and the domains between the cords evolve into a zigzag pattern (b_4 and d_4). Further increase in H finally leads to saturation by simplification of the pattern and rotation of magnetization.

Figure 8. Magnetization process at the surface of the grain-oriented material in fields transverse to the [001] axis. Rows (a) and (b) represent a close-to-perfect Goss texture at room temperature and 550 °C. Rows (c) and (d) represent a moderate crystallographic misorientation relative to Goss texture at room temperature and 550 °C. The images illustrate the magnetization process from the remanent state to +150 mT. Higher-resolution images are provided for finer domain patterns.

In fact, the existence of the checkerboard pattern on the GOES in transverse field was already reported, but for Goss sheets with a thickness of 2 mm [10,19]. The appearance of this pattern in our much thinner sheets is therefore remarkable. Obviously, our 0.27 mm thick GOES, subjected to the transverse magnetic field at 550 °C behaves like a 2 mm thick GOES at room temperature. The checkerboard pattern possesses lower magnetostrictive energy and higher

domain wall energy than the slab domain pattern. One can conclude that at high temperatures, the magnetostrictive energy plays an increased role compared to room temperature as it increases with temperature [27]. Therefore, the more complex checkerboard domains become favored at high temperature compared to the column pattern. The latter would have a higher magnetostrictive energy at elevated temperatures even though it saves on wall energy.

4. Conclusions

Magnetic domain analysis on (110)[001] grain-oriented electrical steel in the temperature range from room temperature to 550 °C leads to the following conclusive remarks:

1. The basic domain width of a nearly perfect (110)[001] grain decreases with increasing temperature as well as demagnetization frequency.
2. An increase in temperature is unfavorable for lancet domains and prevents their formation due to a reduced stray field energy at high temperature. The lancet annihilation temperature is higher for grains with larger misorientation angle.
3. The lancet comb based method for the measurement of out-of-plane misorientation of the (110) surface proved accurate at room temperature. Modifying the method for higher temperatures requires estimating a temperature-dependent correction factor to Bär's model after dedicated systematic measurements.
4. Elevation of temperature characteristically affects the magnetization process of GOES in fields transverse to [001] direction. The checkerboard pattern observed on our 0.27 mm thick sheet above 350 °C is remarkable. Until now, it was only known to exist on GOES sheets thicker than 0.8 mm. In both cases, the domain patterns were determined by magnetostrictive energy rather than domain wall energy. In contrast, when the field was applied in the [001] direction, the effect of temperature was minimal.

References

1. Chen, J.; Chen, Z.; Wang, D.; Wu, L.; Zheng, X.; Birnkammer, F.; Gerling, D. Influence of temperature on magnetic properties of silicon steel lamination. *AIP Advances* **2017**, *7*, 56113, doi:10.1063/1.4978659.
2. Pandey, R.; Weichold, M.; Palmer, D. Materials characterization for high temperature transformers. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **1980**, *16*, 749–751, doi:10.1109/TMAG.1980.1060741.
3. Chen, J.; Wang, D.; Cheng, S.; Wang, Y.; Zhu, Y.; Liu, Q. Modeling of Temperature Effects on Magnetic Property of Nonoriented Silicon Steel Lamination. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **2015**, *51*, 1–4, doi:10.1109/TMAG.2015.2432081.
4. Ferro, A.; Montalenti, G.; Soardo, G. Temperature dependence of power loss anomalies in directional FeSi 3%. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **1976**, *12*, 870–872, doi:10.1109/TMAG.1976.1059112.
5. Hussain, S.; Benabou, A.; Clenet, S.; Lowther, D.A. Temperature Dependence in the Jiles–Atherton Model for Non-Oriented Electrical Steels: An Engineering Approach. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **2018**, *54*, 1–5, doi:10.1109/TMAG.2018.2837126.
6. Pasnak, M.; Lundsten, R. Effects of ultrahigh temperature on magnetic properties of core materials. *Transactions of the American Institute of Electrical Engineers, Part I: Communication and Electronics* **1960**, *78*, 1033–1039, doi:10.1109/TCE.1960.6368513.
7. Takahashi, N.; Morishita, M.; Miyagi, D.; Nakano, M. Comparison of Magnetic Properties of Magnetic Materials at High Temperature. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **2011**, *47*, 4352–4355, doi:10.1109/TMAG.2011.2158517.
8. Boehm, A.; Hahn, I. Measurement of magnetic properties of steel at high temperatures. In *IECON 2014 - 40th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*. IECON 2014 - 40th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society, 2014; pp 715–721, ISBN 1553-572X.
9. Kranz, J.; Brunner, W. Beobachtung Weiß'scher Bereiche auf Siliziumeisen bei hohen Temperaturen. *Zeitschrift für angewandte Physik* **1964**, *19*, 101–108.
10. Hubert, A.; Schäfer, R. *Magnetic Domains: The Analysis of Magnetic Microstructures*, 1st ed.; SpringerSpringer Berlin, Heidelberg, 1998, ISBN 9783540641087.

11. Schäfer, R. Magnetic Domains. In *Handbook of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*; Coey, M., Parkin, S., Eds.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2020; pp 1–44, ISBN 978-3-030-63101-7.
12. Tatsumoto, E.; Okamoto, T. Temperature Dependence of the Magnetostriction Constants in Iron and Silicon Iron. *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan* **1959**, *14*, 1588–1594, doi:10.1143/JPSJ.14.1588.
13. Iwata, K.; Suzuki, M.; Hashimoto, M.; Ueda, M.; Matuoka, Y.; Yasue, T.; Koshikawa, T.; Kotsugi, M.; Ohkochi, T.; Kinoshita, T.; et al. Temperature Dependence of Lancet Domains in Grain-Oriented Fe-3%Si Steels. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **2015**, *51*, 1–4, doi:10.1109/TMAG.2015.2431713.
14. Passon, B. An Application of the magneto-optical Kerr effect for the investigation of fast magnetization processes. *Z. Angew. Physik* **1963**, *16*, 81.
15. Yamamoto, K.; Nakama, I.; Yamashiro, Y. Effect of demagnetization frequency on the stress-effect and domain structure of grain-oriented Si-Fe sheets. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **1999**, *35*, 3793–3795, doi:10.1109/20.800667.
16. Bär, N.; Hubert, A.; Jillek, W. Quantitative untersuchung der supplement-domänenstruktur von kornorientiertem elektroblech A quantitative investigation into the supplementary domain structure of misoriented grains of transformer steel. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* **1977**, *6*, 242–248, doi:10.1016/0304-8853(77)90119-6.
17. He, Z.; Sha, Y.; Zhao, Z.; Zhang, F.; Yang, Y.; Li, G.; Zuo, L. The calculation of magnetic domain and magnetostriction in stressed grain-oriented silicon steel. *Journal of Applied Physics* **2020**, *127*, 35107, doi:10.1063/1.5134854.
18. Iwata, K.; Arai, S.; Ishiyama, K. Calculation of Basic Domain Width Considering Lancet Domains in (110)[001]Fe3%Si. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **2014**, *50*, 353–356, doi:10.1109/TMAG.2013.2283299.
19. Shilling, J.; Houze, G. Magnetic properties and domain structure in grain-oriented 3% Si-Fe. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **1974**, *10*, 195–223, doi:10.1109/TMAG.1974.1058317.
20. Soldatov, I.V.; Zehner, J.; Leistner, K.; Kang, T.; Karnaushenko, D.; Schäfer, R. Advanced, Kerr-microscopy-based MOKE magnetometry for the anisotropy characterisation of magnetic films. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* **2021**, *529*, 167889, doi:10.1016/j.jmmm.2021.167889.
21. Soldatov, I.V.; Schäfer, R. Selective sensitivity in Kerr microscopy. *Review of Scientific Instruments* **2017**, *88*, 73701, doi:10.1063/1.4991820.
22. McCord, J.; Hubert, A. Normalized Differential Kerr Microscopy An Advanced Method for Magnetic Imaging. *phys. stat. sol. (a)* **1999**, *171*, 555–562, doi:10.1002/(SICI)1521-396X(199902)171:2<555:AID-PSSA555>3.0.CO;2-G.
23. Schäfer, R.; Soldatov, I.; Arai, S. Power frequency domain imaging on Goss-textured electrical steel. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials* **2019**, *474*, 221–235, doi:10.1016/j.jmmm.2018.10.100.
24. Lynch, P.A.; Tomus, D.; Bettles, C.J.; Gibson, M.A.; Stevenson, A.W. A comparative EBSD and micro-XRD study of the intergranular grain structure in CP-Ti. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* **2010**, *619*, 298–301, doi:10.1016/j.nima.2009.12.005.
25. Schäfer, R.; Schinnerling, S. Tomography of basic magnetic domain patterns in ironlike bulk material. *Phys. Rev. B* **2020**, *101*, 595, doi:10.1103/PhysRevB.101.214430.
26. Gunes, T.; Schäfer, R.; Derebasi, N. Quantitative Analysis of Magnetic Field Distribution Around Circular Non-Magnetic Region in Grain-Oriented Fe-3%Si Steel. *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **2018**, *54*, 1–8, doi:10.1109/TMAG.2017.2755583.
27. Williams, G.M.; Pavlovic, A.S. The Magnetostriction Behavior of Iron Single Crystals. *Journal of Applied Physics* **1968**, *39*, 571–572, doi:10.1063/1.2163525.